

EBFMC25-OOP-18 · Changes in Thyroid Function Tests and Metabolic Parameters in Obese People Who Lose Weight

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: In the past decades, a number of reports have attempted to explain whether thyroid dysfunction is a cause or a consequence of excess fat tissue, but the answer remains unclear (Walczak & Sieminska, 2021). In this study, we aim to investigate changes in thyroid function tests, insulin resistance, and cholesterol parameters in obese individuals who lose weight.

Materials and Methods: For this research, permission was obtained from the Ethics Committee of KTO University Faculty of Medicine, Non-Drug and Medical Research, numbered 2025/031. This study is cross-sectional, retrospective and was conducted by examining the retrospective data before and after weight loss in the 3-month follow-up of obese individuals aged 18-65 who applied to Konya Beyhekim Training and Research Hospital Obesity Center between January 1, 2022 and January 1, 2025. Changes in thyroid stimulating hormone (TSH), free T4 (fT4), homeostasis model assessment of insulin resistance (HOMA-IR), and cholesterol parameters were evaluated.

Results: A total of 136 obese participants were included in the study. 121 (89.0%) of the participants were female and 15 (11.0%) were male; the median age was 46 (22-67). 97 (71.3%) of the participants were primary school graduates, 39 (28.7%) were high school graduates or higher, 31 (22.8%) were single, 105 (77.2%) were married, 122 (89.7%) were unemployed, 14 (10.3%) were employed, 128 (94.1%) were non-smokers, 8 (5.9%) were smokers, 134 (98.5%) were non-drinkers, and 2 (1.5%) were consuming alcohol. In the second follow-up of the participants, there was a significant decrease in body mass index (BMI) ($p<0.001$), weight ($p=0.001$), hemoglobin A1c (HbA1c) ($p<0.001$), HOMA-IR ($p=0.001$), insulin ($p=0.002$), very low density lipoprotein (VLDL-C) ($p=0.018$), triglyceride (TG) ($p=0.007$), TSH ($p=0.024$), while there was a significant increase in fT4 ($p=0.045$) (Table 1).

Table 1
Comparison of the first and second values of the participants

	Initial Value Median (IQR 25-75%)	Second value Median (IQR 25-75%)	p
TSH (μIU/dL)	2.11 (1.43-3.03)	1.91 (1.40-2.97)	0.024
ft4 (μIU/dL)	1.08 (0.99-1.19)	1.12 (1.06-1.21)	0.045
Total-C (mg/dL)	206 (173-224)	196 (174-223)	0.243
LDL-C (mg/dL)	124 (102-145)	121 (97-140)	0.762
Triglyceride (mg/dL)	122 (85-152)	104 (81-146)	0.007
HDL-C (mg/dL)	52 (45-60)	50 (44-59)	0.402
VLDL-C (mg/dL)	24 (17-30)	21 (16-30)	0.018
FBS (mg/dL)	96 (89-104)	95 (90-104)	0.921
Fasting insulin (IU/ml)	13.17 (9.37-18.03)	10.93 (8.00-16.29)	0.002
HOMA-IR	3.00 (2.07-4.32)	2.35 (1.81-3.92)	0.001
HbA _{1c} (%)	5.70 (5.50-6.00)	5.60 (5.40-5.80)	<0.001
Weight (kg)	97.32 (87.73-105.75)	91.82 (83.95-103.75)	<0.001
BMI (kg/m ²)	37.79 (34.33-41.65)	35.55 (31.75-39.76)	<0.001

Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test, TSH: Thyroid stimulating hormone, ft4: Free tiroglobulin 4, Total-C: Total cholesterol, LDL-C: Low density lipoprotein, HDL-C: High density lipoprotein, VLDL-C: Very low density lipoprotein, FBS: Fasting blood sugar, HOMA-IR: Homeostasis model assessment of insulin resistance, HbA_{1c}: Hemoglobin A_{1c}, BMI: Body mass index

There is a positive significant relationship between the change in BMI of the participants and the change in TSH ($r=0.290$ $p<0.001$), TG ($r=0.246$ $p=0.006$), VLDL-C ($r=0.263$ $p=0.003$), insulin ($r=0.302$ $p=0.001$), HbA1c ($r=0.329$ $p=0.006$) and HOMA-IR ($r=0.304$ $p=0.001$) (Table 2).

Table 2
Relationship between changes in participants' weight and blood parameters

		Δ BMI	Δ Weight	Δ TSH	Δ ft4	Δ TG	Δ VLDL-C	Δ Insulin	Δ HbA _{1c}	Δ HOMA-IR
Δ BMI	r	1.000	0.994	0.290	-0.008	0.246	0.263	0.302	0.329	0.304
	p		<0.001	0.001	0.937	0.006	0.003	0.001	0.006	0.001
Δ Weight	r	0.994	1.000	0.275	-0.025	0.239	0.256	0.328	0.329	0.332
	p	<0.001		0.001	0.798	0.008	0.004	<0.001	0.006	<0.001
Δ TSH	r	0.290	0.275	1.000	-0.234	0.089	0.102	0.072	0.303	0.123
	p	0.001	0.001		0.014	0.330	0.265	0.457	0.011	0.199
Δ ft4	r	-0.008	-0.025	-0.234	1.000	-0.006	0.062	-0.019	-0.006	-0.025
	p	0.937	0.798	0.014		0.950	0.539	0.854	0.965	0.809
Δ TG	r	0.246	0.239	0.089	-0.006	1.000	0.965	0.079	0.006	0.046
	p	0.006	0.008	0.330	0.950		<0.001	0.425	0.963	0.644
Δ VLDL-C	r	0.263	0.256	0.102	0.062	0.965	1.000	0.073	0.022	0.043
	p	0.003	0.004	0.265	0.539	<0.001		0.464	0.856	0.662
Δ Insulin	r	0.302	0.328	0.072	-0.019	0.079	0.073	1.000	0.312	0.935
	p	0.001	<0.001	0.457	0.854	0.425	0.464		0.016	<0.001
Δ HbA _{1c}	r	0.329	0.329	0.303	-0.006	0.006	0.022	0.312	1.000	0.326
	p	0.006	0.006	0.011	0.965	0.963	0.856	0.016		0.012
Δ HOMA-IR	r	0.304	0.332	0.123	-0.025	0.046	0.043	0.935	0.326	1.000
	p	0.001	<0.001	0.199	0.809	0.644	0.662	<0.001	0.012	

Spearman's Rho Test, Δ: Change in given value, BMI: Body mass index, TSH: Thyroid stimulating hormone, ft4: Free tiroglobulin 4, TG: Triglyceride, VLDL-C: Very low density lipoprotein, HbA_{1c}: Hemoglobin A_{1c}, HOMA-IR: Homeostasis model assessment of insulin resistance

Conclusion: As a result of this study, the significant decrease in TSH values and significant increase in ft4 values after obese participants lost weight strengthens the thesis that obesity can cause hypothyroidism. More extensive studies are needed on this subject.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Thyroid stimulating hormone, obesity, insulin resistance, cholesterol

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

REFERENCES

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